

Beyond the Boundary: A Psychological Exploration of Former Cricketers' Unfulfilled Aspirations

Neeta Mehta

Department of Psychology, KET's V. G. Vaze College, Mulund, Mumbai, Maharashtra

In India, cricket is often treated as a religion. It is engaged with great devotion and passionate involvement by those who play it for a career or fun and also by spectators who choose it for entertainment. The glamour and money linked with this profession is so huge that despite the massive inherent uncertainty, cricket as a profession is pursued with great fervour. Given the nature and demands of the sport, the competition to be part of the Indian cricket team is intense. Needless to say, having to give up the dream of becoming a professional cricketer is a painful yet common experience. After making years of arduous journey, what is it to not reach the destination? How does one cope with such a broken dream? In order to answer these questions, a qualitative study was conducted taking 10 cricketers who had gone through serious training and practice but had to give up their dream. Using semi-structured interviews, the study examined their toils and challenges and captured their experience of failing yet bouncing back, utter disappointment yet acceptance and losses yet huge gains of life lessons learnt through a multi-faceted sport called cricket. Thematic analysis revealed 5 overarching themes: (a) Days of Intense Training (b) Struggles and Barriers (c) Emotional Response to Breaking of the Dream (d) Adaptive Coping and Resilience (e) Transfer of Learning From Pitch to Life. The findings emphasize profound impact of cricket in shaping life skills.

Keywords: Cricket, broken dreams, coping, resilience, life skills

Cricket in India is not just a sport, but it is a cultural institution that shapes identities, aspirations and collective experiences. Cricket enjoys intense visibility, financial promise and national prestige. It attracts thousands of young athletes and their parents alike, leading to intense, long-term training and practice sessions, often at the cost of other aspects of life. The entire system, however, is marked by extreme competition, performance pressure and societal disparities. Consequently, one gets to see a high rate of attrition before a handful reach the highest rung. The emotional consequences of broken long-cherished aspirations can be immense. When one's life is seen as equivalent to athletic performance, termination can be highly distressing (Brewer & Petitpas, 2017) especially if it is unplanned or forced, as in cases of injury, selection politics or financial pressures (Park, Lavalley, & Tod, 2013).

In order to understand coping with setbacks in sports, the concept of psychological hardiness is relevant. According to Kobasa (1979), it comprises three dispositions: commitment, control, and challenge. Hardy individuals remain engaged, retain agency during life changes and are more likely to view adversity as an opportunity for growth. Similarly, interpretive frameworks suggest that those who reframe failure through empowering

narratives show better psychological adjustment (Carless & Douglas, 2013).

Huge popularity of cricket is not reflected in qualitative research documenting the voices of those who fail to persevere. This study attempts to address that gap by examining the experiences of former cricketers who discontinued their professional pursuits after years of rigorous engagement. The following questions acted as a guide through this examination:

- What were the toils and challenges experienced during their cricketing journey?
- How did they emotionally experience the breaking of their dreams?
- What coping strategies facilitated their transition?
- What life lessons and psychological competencies did they retain from cricket?

Method

Research Design

In order to explore the journey and the lived experiences of cricketers with unmet dreams, a qualitative phenomenological approach was employed. This approach is suitable to understand how individuals attach meaning to significant life events (Smith, Flowers, & Larkin, 2009).

Participants

Total 10 former cricketers between the age of 28 to 68 years were selected through intentional sampling. Nine of them had undergone serious cricket training for at least 7 years. One took training for 3 years before injury. Each had played at the University or Ranji Trophy levels. All participants had eventually discontinued their pursuit of professional cricket.

Author Note

Dr. Neeta Mehta, Vice Principal, Associate Professor, Head Department of Psychology, KET's V. G. Vaze College, Mulund Mumbai, Maharashtra

I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Dr. Neeta Mehta, Vice Principal, Associate Professor, Head Department of Psychology, KET's V. G. Vaze College, Mulund Mumbai, Maharashtra

E-mail: neetamehta@vazecollege.net

Table 1*Participant Characteristics*

Participant	Age	Period of Training/ Playing (years)	Level Played	Reason for Changing the Career Path
P1	58	11	India Junior Level	Injury and competition
P2	54	12	Bombay Ranji Trophy	Realistic self-assessment, limited opportunities
P3	61	08	Mumbai Under-19; University	Career Shift
P4	56	14	Bombay Ranji Trophy	Competition
P5	51	07	Bombay Ranji Trophy	Realistic self-assessment
P6	58	08	Bombay Ranji Trophy	Stress; lack of exposure, limited opportunities
P7	29	15	University of Mumbai	Lack of visibility/exposure
P8	68	10	Bank of India Cricket	Limited opportunities
P9	57	08	Bombay Ranji Trophy	Injury
P10	28	03	University Level	Injury

Data Collection

Data was collected online using a semi-structured interview guide. This guide covered participants' entry into cricket, daily training schedule and struggles, challenges faced over a period of time, decision to discontinue and emotional response to that decision, their strategies for coping and adaptation and their assessment of impact of cricket on their lives. Interviews were in-depth and lasted for about 45 to 90 minutes and were recorded with informed consent.

Data Analysis

Recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim. They were examined to uncover a thematic pattern (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The process involved the following steps:

- Familiarization with transcripts
- Initial coding of meaningful units
- Grouping codes into preliminary themes
- Refining and reviewing themes
- Defining and naming themes
- Synthesizing findings into broader interpretive categories

Results and Discussion

Days of Intense Training

All the participants of the study shared their demanding daily schedules involving morning and evening practice, attending college and weekend matches. Quotes such as “There was an element of madness do anything and everything just make sure that you are there where you intend to be”(P4) and “I gave 125 percent” (P5) communicated unyielding dedication that the sport demanded. Commitment was not limited to physical effort; it caused significant mental exertion. As P5 noted, “Overcoming disappointment of not getting wickets, catches getting dropped, getting dropped from the team, not getting selected... How to recoup yourself mentally and come back the next day and say, okay, they didn't select me this time but I will perform better...”. This level of sustained effort resonates with Vallerand's (2015) theory of passion. It explains that despite substantial physical and psychological toil, if motivation is internalized and the athlete's identity is deeply formed, then it can lead to persistence.

Struggles and Barriers

Several major themes indicating the above point emerged:

- Financial Pressures

Financial challenges were mentioned by all except one young participant. It was narrated as the main push factor away from cricket.

“India was a shortage economy - in that shortage economy, you had to think what will you do for living. Post 1990 - abundance economy came. Now there are opportunities dime a dozen. Those days opportunities not there. ...in shortage economy expectation was that you contribute towards family income” (P2)

Research by Ryba, Ronkainen, and Selänne (2013) supports this observation, showing how socioeconomic barriers often compel athletes to deprioritise their sporting aspirations.

- Balancing academics with cricket

For middle class families, education is a ladder to success. So, striking a balance between study and cricket was one of challenges participants talked about and majority of them could not really do a good balancing except one (P2) of them.

“I did not balance - till 10th std I studied only and next 7 years I played -- studied last minute and passed. Then once I stopped playing, I focused on the studies again ...You can't sail in two boats. (P5)

The one who shared successful balancing of studies and cricket talked about Catch 22 situation with respect to having plan B for cricket.

“...If you have to succeed in the game, you have to give it everything. You cannot have plan B. ...In those days, plan B was essential. ...I think you assess yourself down the line ... only 11 people can play for the country ...are you among those 11 people. ...On the basis of that you then deprioritize and do other things”(P2)

Findings from recent research corroborate participants' narratives about typical education-sport dilemma. For instance, Sun et al. (2023) showed how college-level athletes experience negative emotions and reduced life satisfaction due to this conflict. Similarly, Mishra (2024) highlights how academic performance can get adversely impacted, especially when time and effort demand exceed students' capacity.

- Career-ending Injuries

Four participants (P1, P7, P9, & P10) talked about injuries that they suffered as a significant challenge and how they were replaced by others in their absence. In case of two of them, it was the primary

reason for quitting the professional cricket. Literature on athletes' health clearly indicates that musculoskeletal injuries are often cited as a reason for involuntary retirement and are linked with anxiety, depression, and distress (Furie, Park, & Wong, 2023).

- Systemic barriers.

Lack of information or guidance (P1, P6), luck (P6) and parental opposition to take cricket as a profession (P1, P6), peer pressure (P10) were additional challenges some of these cricketers had to deal with.

Emotional Response to Breaking of the Dream

Two young participants explicitly expressed the difficulty they experienced while coming to terms with the situation - they called that period as one of the toughest periods of their lives.

"It broke me as a person. I was very disturbed for a couple of years. It was my dream and passion to play cricket. ... It hurts me right now also"(P10)

Research by Roberts, Mullen, Evans, and Hall (2015) revealed the similar negative psychological reactions such as feelings of loss, resentment, and identity disruption to career termination in case of retired professional cricketers.

Older participants reported fewer explicit emotions, likely due to retrospective distance and generational norms discouraging emotional disclosure.

Adaptive Coping and Resilience

The dominant coping mechanism was reality-based appraisal, including acknowledgment of limited opportunities, acceptance of one's skill level relative to peers and assessment of family and financial responsibilities.

"I had to be realistic with myself - I said no point chasing the dream or mirage - then you are too old to study, too old to play either. The only reason I stopped playing because I was not good enough. I have to be honest with myself and with you (P5)

"I got to know that I had to I draw the line somewhere. ...So, I accepted. Gracefully accepted and then shifted. I knew that there are better cricketers than me. They are doing well..." (P1)

These participants could appropriately discern what was under their control and what was not. By accepting that they had given their best and could do nothing beyond their control (due to luck factor & better cricketers), they showed an adaptive external locus of control too that helped them respond appropriately.

These findings related to adaptive coping are in line with research by Grove, Lavallee, and Gordon (1997).

Most Participants demonstrated hardiness traits: Commitment (purposeful involvement with life goals), Control: focusing on what could be changed and Challenge (viewing transitions as growth opportunities) - consistent with hardiness literature (Kobasa, 1979; Maddi, 2002).

Remaining connected with cricket, a sense of gratitude for having played with the best cricketers, reading inspirational books, and seeking guidance from the mentor were some of the additional coping strategies used by the participants to move on. Despite losing their original dream, participants reframed the experience as a temporary setback, transformative and foundational to later success. This meaning-making exemplifies post-traumatic growth and aligns with psychological resilience literature (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 2004) The study demonstrated the tenet of "What Hurts, Heals Too" - when

it comes to cricket, one always wins, even when one loses.

Transfer of Learning from Pitch to Life

The most important and significant insight from the study is about the role of cricket, which all participants (10) highlighted in coping with their lives without cricket. Rather, there was not a sense of failure at all that any of them talked about, but only lessons learned and life skills inculcated. Despite repeated setbacks and eventual quitting of one's passion, participants did not exhibit helplessness. On the contrary, there was optimism ever-present deep belief that things will work out and what works out is the best for me. Each participant shared the beautiful transfer of training and enduring lessons that they have learned from cricket: relationship building skills (P1), humility and resilience (P10), decision making (P5), patience (P3), teamwork and leadership (P7). All the latent and tacit learning and knowledge were carried forward to a new arena. In the words of P2, "To that extent cricket gives you simulation of what happens in life. ..." and P5 maintained "...whatever I learned in cricket field, I did not learn it in any classroom or boardroom. ... Cricket has been the best university I have been to"

Many participants expressed their feelings regarding their broken dreams in cricket terminology. P1 emphasized perseverance that cricket taught him: "You should fight, till the last ball". P2 highlighted on need to start afresh after every disappointment by saying, "You are only as good as the last ball you have faced. P6 shared about how he developed strength to take failure in his stride and P5 learned to be balanced in life, which supported him later in his professional career.

For the participants, their training in cricket also helped them achieve cognitive and emotional regulation. For example, P4 shared how cricket taught him how to disconnect from past and future and to focus on the present: "...in cricket ... you focus on the ball that you are facing you don't think of the past that has gone or the future that is going to come. I guess that helped me a lot. In disconnecting". Another participant (P6) reflected on how he acquired the power to discern - knowing "which ball to play and which to leave," an analogy he used to explain his approach to decision-making in life. Another huge benefit that was shared was character building when one learns to accept things beyond one's control, as in cricket - team dynamics, environmental conditions, and luck - all of which cultivate humility and adaptability (P2).

de Subijana, Gutiérrez, and Meler (2024) in their research work, demonstrated that British elite swimmers, acquire life skills including emotional regulation, resilience, decision-making, and social competence that go beyond the sporting arenas.

In essence, cricket seemed to have honed emotional intelligence skills of these participants - especially skill of not ruminating on the past but celebrate the present and welcome the future. As P10 summarized, "sports teaches you everything. ... You learn sportsman spirit first of all, you learn to be patient, you learn to persevere under pressure. You learn the temperament. You learn to bear the pain. You learn to fight. You learn to fight with a smile. You learn not to be content with small successes. You always learn to look at the bigger picture. You always learn to get back when you fall".

The study clearly demonstrated that, despite frustrations and setbacks, participants cultivated fortitude and understanding, as frustratingly put in the quote, "Life is an endless struggle, full of frustrations and challenges. But eventually you find a hairstylist you like."

Limitations of the Study

The findings of the study are limited by the small sample ($N=10$) of the study. Most of the participants were in age group of above 50, which might have compromised their memory of all the emotions that they experienced when they had to shift their focus away from the cricket. Besides, we are talking about that age group of men whose socialization might have taught them not to talk about their feelings. To that extent, the participants' sharing was more about how they adapted and moved on rather than what they felt and how they suffered, if at all they suffered.

Conclusion

The study reveals that the breaking of a cherished cricketing dream was indeed an emotionally painful experience. Yet, all was not lost. Years of training and practice of playing cricket were equivalent to life training. Former cricketers demonstrated remarkable introspection, effective coping, resilience and adaptive life transitions. Cricket served as an instrument for character development, emotional intelligence, discipline and life skills such as patience, decision-making, teamwork that extended beyond the boundaries of the sport. The findings underscore importance of building psychological support systems for athletes as well as the enduring strengths that sports can nurture.

References

- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Brewer, B. W., & Petitpas, A. J. (2017). Athletic identity foreclosure. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 16, 118-122.
- Carless, D., & Douglas, K. (2013). Living, resisting, and playing the part of athlete: Narrative tensions in elite sport. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 14(5), 701-708.
- de Subijana, C., Gutiérrez, M., & Meler, M. (March 2024). British elite swimmers' experiences and perspectives on life skill development: What sport gives you beyond the pool. *Frontiers in Psychology*.
- Furie, K., Park, A. L., & Wong, S.E. (2023). Mental health and involuntary retirement from sports post-musculoskeletal injury in adult athletes: A systematic review. *Current Reviews in Musculoskeletal Medicine*, 16, 211-219.
- Grove, J. R., Lavallee, D., & Gordon, S. (1997). Coping with retirement from sport: The influence of athletic identity. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 9(2), 191-203.
- Kobasa, S. C. (1979). Stressful life events, personality, and health: An inquiry into hardiness. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 37(1), 1-11.
- Maddi, S. R. (2002). The story of hardiness: Twenty years of theorizing, research, and practice. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 54(3), 173-185.
- Mishra, S. (2024). Impact of sports participation on academic performance. *Innovations in Sports Science*, 1(3), 11-16.
- Park, S., Lavallee, D., & Tod, D. (2013). Athletes' career transition out of sport: A systematic review. *International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 6(1), 22-53.
- Roberts, C.M., Mullen, R., Evans, L., & Hall, R. (2015). An in-depth appraisal of career termination experiences in professional cricket. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 33(9), 935-44.
- Ryba, T. V., Ronkainen, N. J., & Selänne, H. (2013). Elite athletic career as a cultural journey. In N. Stambulova and T. V. Ryba (Eds.). *Athletes' careers across cultures*. London: Routledge.
- Smith, J. A., Flowers, P., & Larkin, M. (2009). *Interpretative phenomenological analysis: Theory, method and research*. London: Sage.
- Sun, W., Liu, L., Jiang, Y., Fang, P., Ding, X., & Wang, G. (2023). Academics-athletics conflict and college athletes' well-being: The mediating effect of negative emotions and the moderating effect of life motivation. *Behavioural Sciences*, 13(2), 93.
- Tedeschi, R. G., & Calhoun, L. G. (2004). Posttraumatic growth: Conceptual foundations and empirical evidence. *Psychological Inquiry*, 15(1), 1-18.
- Vallerand, R. J. (2015). *The psychology of passion: A dualistic model*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Received October 14, 2025

Revision received October 26, 2025

Accepted October 30, 2025